

Cult of Atargatis in Dura Europos

also known as “Temple of Atargatis Dura-Europos”

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It concerns the worship of the goddess Atargatis in the Syro-Mesopotamian city of Dura-Europos, located on the Euphrates. This entry concerns people, cultic personnel, place of women and organization of the worship of the Syrian Goddess in this particular city. This is an outcome on the research of the project AI-At: People of the Gods. The Worshipers of Allat and Atargatis in the Near East from the 4th century BCE to the 4th c. CE financed within the program Polonez Bis 1: No. 2021/43/P/HS3/02595 co-funded by the National Science Centre (Poland) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 945339

Date Range: 1 CE - 256 CE

Region: Dura-Europos

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia

Syria

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Women

– Other [specify]

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We can assume that the political entity allowed construction of the temple in the city space. It was for sure built by a cultic association.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not in any source a hint about an involvement of the goddess in the construction of the place.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: nothing is preserved from the sacred literature. However we can assume that there were some sacred texts concerning the cult of Atargatis.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Body of water (as distinct from source)

Type of elevation

- Other [specify]

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

- No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

- Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: The temple of Atargatis in Dura-Europos stands on the remains of Hellenistic-early Parthian houses.

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

- I don't know

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1
- Source 2
- Source 3

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: From 1928 for 10 subsequent years joint archaeological mission American-French, led by Michail Rostovtzeff from Yale University and Franz Cumont and Maurice Pillet was making regular excavations on the site bringing to light many fascinating results. In the campaign 1936-37 this mission explored further the temple of Atargatis finding epigraphic material.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name

Years of excavation:

– Year range

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: This is the last archaeological mission which worked until 2011 in Dura Europos, led by prof. Pierre Leriche from the Ecole Normale Supérieure in Paris. They managed in the last years to introduce the name Europos-Doura of the site.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name

Years of excavation:

– Year range

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Illicit

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Pre-modern

Notes: The site got attention by the accidental discovery of the well preserved paintings by the British soldiers stationing in the neighboring Salihiyeh in 1920. Short visits of F. Cumont and works of J. Breasted made foundations for future archaeological works in the site.

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL
- Source 1 Description
- Source 2 URL
- Source 2 Description

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: More-or-less. The temple has also an "odeon", a room with theatrical shaped benches with the names of women of Dura-Europos.

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: To the temple of Atargatis belongs also a structure called "House of Priests".

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: It has also additional rooms.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The temple of Atargatis is adjacent to the temple of Artemis

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Social

Notes: The gatherings had a social dimension. There was a group called hetaireia in a Greek inscription which was responsible for building a meeting room, probably for the purposes of feasting. The "odeon" was also dedicated for meetings, especially in the female circle.

– Sacrificial

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The temple of Atargatis is adjacent to the temple of Artemis. There are also rooms and buildings attached to the temple of Atargatis (House of Priests and the Salle-a-gradins)

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The rooms are smaller, salle-a-gradins is the largest room, in the middle of the temple building the courtyard is of big dimensions.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: The size of the temple is of a size of a building unit in Dura-Europos. It is house-like architecture.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It could be that certain elements in the temple were wooden. However nothing of this sort was ever discovered on site.

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

Notes: List of the members of the hetaireia and the inscriptions on the stair-benches in the "odeon".

↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:
– Yes

Notes: There are some dedications, the most important one was made in 20. September 34 CE when the association dedicated a construction of a room for the goddess. It contains the signatures of all members of the association.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The state of preservation of the walls is very poor and low, we can only assume that there were some decorations outside as well.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There are graffiti, inscriptions and one of the texts informs about phalloi set in the courtyard (nowadays not preserved). There were also reliefs and statues.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They were not discovered.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: nothing of this sort was found, however there are paintings in Dura Europos representing the deities.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: On the relief there are lions flanking the throne of the goddess.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There is a stela with sign of the Moon God Sin-Maralahe, worshipped in Harran.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: See above: Atargatis.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Atargatis with her divine husband Hadad.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: A standard with ribbons and moon crescent.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know if in this temple the oneiromancy was practiced.

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were ritual dances, but we do not know anything about the trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the sources do not mention the practice

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through a monarch:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral gods

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ other:

– Other [specify]

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: This is not clear.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The cult statue was never found

Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: The signs of communication are dedications.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: no space for large-scale rituals

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify

Notes: to maintain the cult

– specify

Notes: during the festivals

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know anything about it, sources are lacking.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Not in this case, the personnel is local coming from Dura. However in the cult of Atargatis in Delos there are people from the Northern Syria, mostly Hierapolis-Manbij.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: There are headmasters of associations and high priests.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: male (hetaireia); women in the "odeon" and eunuchs according to the tradition (Lucian of Samosata)

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no sources which would indicate the controlling of economic resources, however from analogies to other temples we can think that the temple must have had own animals and other resources for functioning.

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

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General References

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